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MAPPING PERFUME FRAGRANCES FOR PACKAGING DESIGN

EXPLORING ARCHETYPICAL DESIGN CHARACTERISTICS IN CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Consumers often rely on the design of packages to inform themselves about products. It is therefore important to establish a link between the package and the product inside. However, few studies describe how designers practically can go about in achieving this linkage in packaging design. In this paper, we describe the design process underlying the creation of a new perfume bottle concept. In the case of perfume, the bottle needs to provide consumers cues about the content (scent) inside. Therefore, consumer insights on the link between design and product characteristics were therefore explored during the design process. 450 female participants rated 32 non-branded bottles with respect to the scents and metaphors they expressed. The bottles were systematically altered in terms of roundness, elongation, material and color. The results unveiled associations between bottle design characteristics, scent characteristics and (advertising) metaphors. In the design process, we explored these results further through the use of a perceptual map. The paper describes how we went about in developing the perceptual map.

Keywords: packaging, perfume, perceptual map

INTRODUCTION

The choice of perfume is an important one. Scent is closely tied to emotions. Therefore, what perfume someone wears directly effects this person and those around him or her emotionally. The choice of perfume is also seen as a reflection of a person's personality with different perfumes symbolizing different types of people. Thus, when buying

perfumes, people do not only buy a scent but also the emotions and meanings associated with it. However, to select the right perfume to buy is often easier said than done. First, in stores, perfumes are sold next to each other, making it hard to differentiate the scent of one perfume from another. Second, the 'true' scent of a perfume (e.g. the lightness of its scent) is only experienced in actual use on the body. Yet, in many cases, the person buying a perfume is not necessarily the one that will be using it. This means that consumers seldom can rely on the "actual" scent of a perfume (its intrinsic product characteristic) when buying it. When people cannot rely on intrinsic product characteristics, they need to base their choice on extrinsic cues such as advertising and packaging. Indeed, in the perfume industry, companies often rely on advertising and packaging to communicate the scent of perfumes. However, while scholars have addressed the role of advertising in this industry (see e.g. Velasco-Sacristan & Fuertes-Olivera, 2006), the role of packaging has received less attention. In this paper, we address this gap in the literature. Specifically, we concentrate on the way perfume packages (bottles) are designed to underscore the scent of perfumes. In design, it is well-known that people derive meanings from products and that designers can fulfill an important role in manipulating those meanings (see e.g. Vihma, 1995). Several studies address how people recognize meanings that were 'designed' into products (Smets and Overbeeke, 1995, Orth and Malkewitz, 2008). Govers, Hekkert and Schoormans (2004) showed that consumers recognized product personality traits in products, and that such traits can be consciously embodied into the product appearance. Based on a study on physical product

interaction, Desmet, Ortíz Nicolás and Schoormans (2008) concluded that it is possible to design products with different interaction personalities. With respect to packaging design, several studies address how people infer beliefs about olfactory (scent) characteristics from packaging characteristics such as color (Desmatte et al, 2008) and shape (see e.g. Xue & Yen, 2007).

The studies above suggest that design can fulfill an important role in underscoring the scents (and meanings) of perfumes. Still, in the packaging design literature, there are few methods available to support designers in this role. And, in the case there are methods, the literature seldom report on the use of them.

In the paper, we describe the process followed in a design project for a new perfume bottle concept for a well-known fashion brand. In particular, we outline how consumer insights on the link between design and product characteristics were studied and integrated in the project. The objective of the project was to develop a perfume bottle for a new fragrance for women. The fragrance was to be sensual and mature with a woody oriental scent, and the brand owner was now looking for a way to embody this in the bottle design. In the project, we constructed a perceptual map on bottle design, scent and metaphors, and used it as a starting point for the design of the new bottle. Departing from the

three-step method outlined by Schoormans et al (2010), the development of the perceptual map constitutes the scope of this paper.

THE PERFUME INDUSTRY: SCENTS AND METAPHORS

Perfume fragrances come in a blend of different scents. In distinguishing between different fragrances, industry experts often turn to the model of the French Perfumers Society (Société Française des Parfumeurs). The model allows experts to classify fragrance of perfumes on key scent characteristics such as floral and wooden. Based on this model, Jellinek (1992) developed a system that describes fragrances - and their desired effects on consumers - by mapping common perfume scents on two dimensions. The two dimensions are: (1) 'light' to 'heavy' and (2) 'floral' to 'less floral'. Together, the dimensions provide industry experts a basis for understanding people's reactions to perfumes. The meanings people associate with perfumes (and perfume brands) are often abstract. Therefore, perfume companies often rely on metaphors to communicate scent (and brand) characteristics to consumers. In perfume advertising (targeted towards women), metaphors about *romanticism/love*, *sensuality/sexuality*, *elegance/avant-gardism* and *action/dynamism* are commonly used (Velasco-Sacristan & Fuertes-Olivera; 2006).

Figure 1. Dimensions of perfume scents combined with major advertisement metaphors

DATA COLLECTION: MAPPING BOTTLE CHARACTERISTICS, SCENTS AND METAPHORS

In developing the new bottle concept, it was deemed important to establish a link between the new bottle and the fragrance of the perfume inside. In other words, by systematically altering the shape and color of the new bottle, the goal was that consumers should be able to recognize the scent of the perfume without having to open the bottle.

To achieve this goal, we developed a perceptual map on perfume scents, metaphors and bottle design to more systematically integrate consumer insights into the project. Departing from an adjusted version of the three-step method of Schoormans et al (2010), we followed the following steps in developing the perceptual map.

STEP 1: METAPHORS AND SCENTS

The four major metaphors noted above (romance, elegance, action and sensuality) fit well with the scent characteristics in Jellink's system. The metaphor *romanticism/love* is supplementary with kindness, tenderness and affection and is highly associated to floral fragrances. *Action/dynamism* is supplementary to vitality, magnetism and energy and is associated with citrus fragrances. Therefore, we began by mapping the metaphors on Jellink's original classification system (see Figure 1).

STEP 2: PRE-STUDY

In uncovering important links between bottle designs and perfume characteristics (scents and metaphors), we performed a small pre-study. The purpose of the pre-study was (1) to distinguish commonly used colors and shapes in perfume bottles and (2) to investigate to what degree scent characteristics and metaphors were associated with different bottle designs.

We began by selecting 15 bottles from the most sold perfume brands in the Netherlands. Next, 15 women categorized the bottles according to the defining characteristics of their design. They also indicated the degree they associated different scents and metaphors to the different bottles.

The pre-test suggested that roundness, elongation, color and material all influenced anticipations about scent. As shown in figure 2, the bottles distributed themselves over the two scent dimensions (floral to less floral and light to heavy). Floral scents were associated with pink color. Heavy scents were associated with compact dark colored bottles. The results also suggested that each of the four metaphors were associated with different bottle designs and perfume fragrances.

STEP 3: MAIN STUDY

Departing from the results of the pre-test, we devised an online questionnaire to collect (quantitative) data for the development of our

Figure 2. Pre-test results on the dimensions florality and lightness

us to understand what metaphors they associated with different bottle designs. Here, color proved to be the most discriminating design characteristics. Next, we made the results more actionable for the project by integrating them with our earlier extension of Jellinek's classification system. The result was a perceptual map where links between scent, metaphors and bottle design could be explored. For example, as shown in the map (see Figure 3), scents associated with romance strongly related to roundness but had no clear relation with the elongation or compactness of the design. Heavier scents were associated with more compact and angular designs.

FINAL REMARKS

When people cannot rely on intrinsic product characteristics (such as the smell of a perfume on the body), they need to rely on extrinsic cues such as packaging of a product to acquire information about the product inside. Still, in the packaging design literature, there are few reports on how designers can go about in collecting information about how consumers infer beliefs about product characteristics on basis of packaging designs.

In this paper, exemplifying past work of Schoormans et al (2010), we described how links between scents, metaphors and bottle designs were explored during a design project. The goal of the project was to develop a perfume bottle for a well-known fashion

brand. The fragrance of the perfume was to be sensual and mature with a woody oriental scent. Departing from the results of a consumer study, three bottle designs were developed with the help of a perceptual map. The desired scents and metaphors were recognized in all the concepts by the brand owner.

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